

Title: Deep Learning in Fake News Evaluation

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INTRODUCTION:

The concept of “Fake News” consisting of article content exceeding the bounds of fact based journalism has become an increasing problem over the past year. In this talk we explore real world use case applications for automated “Fake News” evaluation using contemporary deep learning article vectorization and tagging.

We begin with the use case and an evaluation of the appropriate context applications for various deep learning applications in fake news evaluation. Technical material will review several methodologies for article vectorization with classification pipelines, ranging from traditional to advanced deep architecture techniques. We close with a discussion on troubleshooting and performance optimization when consolidating and evaluating these various techniques on active data sets.

AIM:

Articles are vectorized and then assessed along various dimensions misaligned with pure fact based journalism (bias, hate speech, editorial, etc). The resulting algorithms aim to provide the user with tags for these misaligned dimensions in order to flag when a processed article fails to adhere to pure fact based journalism.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Algorithms were trained using the Google Cloud Platform infrastructure, processing several years of examples of scraped articles identified as representative of each of the specified tag types. Algorithms used include word and sentence embedding NLU algorithms including both traditional paragraph vectorization and RNN based architectures.

RESULTS:

Offline results in both precision and recall scores for each tag are remarkably high. The algorithms both perform strongly on open sourced tagged data sets such as the kaggle set and on our much more comprehensive internal benchmarks. Challenges still exist with open ended submission. Future work will aim at filtering out non-article based submissions to focus live production scope.

CONCLUSIONS:

According to the work presented here, Fake-News challenges framed as a detection of non-journalism based flagging algorithms is a tractable problem and can be successfully addressed with the presented techniques.

KEYWORDS:

Fake News, LSTM, Word2Vec, Doc2Vec, NLU

BIOGRAPHY:

Mike serves as Head of Data Science at Uber ATG, UC Berkeley Data Science faculty, and head of SkyMind Labs the research lab affiliated with DeepLearning4J. He has led teams of Data Scientists in the bay area as Chief Data Scientist for InterTrust, Director of Data Sciences for MetaScale/Sears, and CSO for Galvanize where he founded the galvanizeU-UNH accredited Masters of Science in Data Science degree and oversaw the company's transformation from co-working space to Data Science organization.